

Multibeneficial natural material – Dye from heartwood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk.^ψ

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Material isolated from the heartwood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* is found to be of multiple diversified use. It could be used as a direct dye for wool and silk; had a sufficient antibacterial activity against certain bacteria the gram positive *Bacillus subtilis*, *B. cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram negative *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and finds several medicinal uses; could be used as a neutralization indicator in wider range of concentrations (10^{-2} to 4 N) than the conventional indicators. The structures of the indicator in acid and basic mediums suggested.

The dyes obtained from plant materials sometimes have multiple diverse uses. They can be used as the colorants for cloth, paper, wool etc. and altogether they may have a very good medicinal value and they may also have their use in Analytical Chemistry in volumetric analysis in the form of neutralisation indicators. Two such naturally occurring materials are from the heartwood of *Caesalpinia sappan*^{1,2} and roots of *Arnebia nobilis*³⁻⁵. The material isolated from the heartwood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* is found to be another such important medicinal dye. *Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lamk., syn. *A. integrifolia* Linn., family moraceae, commonly known as 'Jack tree' (*Kathal* in Hindi) is a large evergreen tree cultivated throughout the hotter parts of India. Heartwood of plant is a source of varied coloured medicinal dyes. The plant was first screened for its component morin⁶ present in the heartwood, a way back in 1895. When extracted with methanol, heartwood yields a red coloured decoction, which on removal of solvent yields a dark red-brown semi-solid dye.

Various parts of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* have been in use as a traditional medicine in Southeast Asia⁷⁻¹⁴ to treat many conditions such as skin diseases, diarrhoea, fever, bilious colic and diabetes etc. In Cambodia, wood is considered a nervous sedative, and administered in convulsions. Morin, a yellow colouring flavonoid has diuretic activity. Antiprogesterational activity of morin in rats has also been demonstrated¹⁵. Methanolic extract of heartwood is antibacterial against cariogenic bacteria. Two active compounds 6-(3-methyl-1-butenyl)-5,2',4'-trihydroxy-3-isoprenyl-7-methoxyflavone and 5,7,2',4'-tetrahydroxy-6-isoprenyl-

flavone completely inhibited the growth of primary cariogenic bacteria¹⁶. They also exhibited the growth inhibitory effect on plaque-forming streptococci. These isoprenylflavones would be potent compounds for prevention of dental caries¹⁶. Dyeing property of the heartwood extracted material for silk was first reported¹⁷ in 1907. It had also been used in Mithila paintings, the plant symbolizing reverences of forefather's fertility and focussing¹⁸. Dye has a colour changing property in acid and basic mediums and therefore the possibility of its use as a natural indicator for neutralization titration existed. All the three aspects were investigated in the present work in the form of dyeing character, antimicrobial studies and neutralisation indicator studies.

Results and discussion

Dyeing properties :

Red-brown dye from heartwood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* was tried on cotton, silk, wool and paper as a direct dye. Fresh, 15 days, one month, three months and one year old dyed samples gave very satisfactory results for their fastness against ageing, light, and soap washing in the case of animal fibres – wool and silk, but not so good for the paper and the vegetable fibre – cotton. Some of the constituents of the dye are the flavonoids morin (1), artocarpesin (2) and cycloartocarpesin (3) etc. It is an acid dye (phenolic). Certain synthetic phenolic dyes like Martius yellow and Orange I are already in use as the direct dyes. In such dyes the fixing is probably through H-bonding.

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Antimicrobial studies :

The isolated dye showed the inhibition on the growth of six pathogenic bacteria studied¹⁹. Zone of inhibition, as an average of three sets, are given in Table 1. Largest inhibition was towards *Bacillus subtilis* and *B. cereus*. *B. subtilis* is an opportunistic bacterium and can cause egg infection and septicemia, contaminate blood transfusion bottles and haemolyse the blood. *B. cereus* is responsible for food poisoning, as it can grow on food and produce an enterotoxin that causes diarrhoea. Growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* is moderately inhibited. The bacterium is distinguished by its production of coagulase and various toxins and causes boils, carbuncles, abscesses and some deep seated septic infections like osteomyelitis. Growths of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli* were also inhibited. Former is sometimes the cause of pneumonia and associated with urinary

and respiratory infections while the latter is a well known member of the flora of gastrointestinal tract causing gastroenteritis, pyelitis and cystitis. Response of this dye on *Salmonella typhi*, causative agent of typhoid and persistent diarrhoea in human, gastroenteritis in swine and abortions in sheep and equines, was also moderate. The broad inhibitory spectrum of dye indicated its usefulness in syrups, ointments and lotions etc. However toxicological studies need to be done before recommending its application in different preparations for human use.

Neutralisation indicator :

Results of the volumetric titrations for varied concentrations of acid and alkali using the isolated natural dye as indicator are given in Table 2, along with a comparative study with conventional indicators phenolphthalein and methyl orange. Results of pH-metric titrations are given in Table 3 alongwith λ_{max} values of the dye at the equivalence points of acid-base titrations. It is concluded from above results, in no way the natural dye obtained from *Artocarpus heterophyllus* is an inferior indicator than the popular phenolphthalein and methyl orange indicators for different types of neutralisation titrations. Instead it is better in range. A successful titration of $10^{-2} N$ acid-alkali could be performed by the natural dye whereas this could not give satisfactory end point when phenolphthalein was used. Moreover, while phenolphthalein failed in strong acid-weak base, and methyl orange failed in weak acid-strong base, this natural indicator was successful in strong acid-weak base as well as weak acid-strong base in all of tried ranges of titrations.

In the case of phenolphthalein, in presence of dilute alkali, the lactone ring opens and the triphenylcarbinol structure undergoes loss of water to produce resonating ion²⁰,

Table 1. Inhibitory effect of the dye on pathogenic bacteria

Organism	Inhibition zone (mm)
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> MTCC 430	14.4
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> MTCC 1789	14.8
<i>Escherichia coli</i> MTCC 1591	8.7
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> MTCC 2405	10.1
<i>Salmonella typhi</i> MTCC 531	11.4
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> MTCC 87	12.0

Table 2. Results of three kinds of titrations

Vol. of acid taken = 10 mL

Strong acid-strong base titrations :

HCl <i>N</i>	NaOH <i>N</i>	Volume of NaOH required		Present dye indicator		Phenolphthalein	
		Present dye indicator	Phenolphthalein	Colour change at equiv. point	Sharpness and stability upto atleast 1 min	Colour change at equiv. point	Sharpness and stability upto atleast 1 min
0.01	0.01	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Disappears soon
0.10	0.10	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
1.00	1.00	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
4.00	4.00	10.00	9.95	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable

Strong acid-weak base titrations :

HCl <i>N</i>	NH ₄ OH <i>N</i>	Volume of NH ₄ OH required		Present dye indicator		Methyl orange	
		Present dye indicator	Methyl orange	Colour change at equiv. point	Sharpness and stability upto atleast 1 min	Colour change at equiv. point	Sharpness and stability upto atleast 1 min
0.01	0.01	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable
0.10	0.10	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable
1.00	1.00	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable
4.00	4.00	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Pink to yellow	Sharp Stable

Weak acid-strong base titrations :

CH ₃ COOH <i>N</i>	NaOH <i>N</i>	Volume of NaOH required		Present dye indicator		Phenolphthalein	
		Present dye indicator	Phenolphthalein	Colour change at equiv. point	Sharpness and stability upto atleast 1 min	Colour change at equiv. point	Sharpness and stability upto atleast 1 min
0.01	0.01	10.05	10.05	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
0.10	0.10	10.05	10.05	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
1.00	1.00	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable
4.00	4.00	10.00	10.00	Creamish to Mustard yellow	Sharp Stable	Colourless to pink	Sharp Stable

which is red. But in excess alkali the red colour disappears owing to the conversion to benzenoid structure. In the case of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* one of the main active coloured constituents is cycloartocarpesin (3) which is a bit compa-

rable to phenolphthalein. Pure cycloartocarpesin was also iso-lated and verified as described by Parthasarthy *et al.*²¹. Similar titrations, leading to same conclusions, were carried out but because of a single substance, the range was

Table 3. pH-metric titrations and λ_{\max} values

Vol. of acid or alkali taken = 25 mL, [Acid]=1.0 N, [Alkali] = 1.0 N						
Type of titration	Volume of alkali added (mL)	pH	Colour	Colour change	λ_{\max} nm	λ_{\max} nm (reverse titration)
Strong acid-strong base	24.95	3.30	Creamish	Sharp	324	335
	25.00	9.36	Mustard yellow	Sharp		
Strong acid-weak base	24.95	4.07	Creamish	Sharp	324	335
	25.00	7.42	Mustard yellow	Sharp		
Weak acid-strong base	24.95	6.21	Creamish	Sharp	323	334
	25.00	9.54	Mustard yellow	Sharp		

narrower. The natural dye is creamish in leuco form but mustard yellow in quinonoid form. It seems that a change from quinonoid form to benzenoid form in excess alkali, as in phenolphthalein, does not take place in the case of cycloartocarpesin. However, in alkaline medium cycloartocarpesin possesses mustard yellow colour due to the salt formation and assumption of quinonoid form in dihydric phenolic ring.

Results shown in Table 2 indicate only a single stage of colour change like the phenolphthalein and methyl orange but unlike the *Caesalpinia sappan* dye² natural indicator. It is explained on the basis of structures 3 and 3A supported by obtaining of two types of λ_{\max} values in the solution at equivalence point.

Experimental

Isolation of dye: Authentic heartwood of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* was procured locally from Hardwar. 50 g of heartwood chips were refluxed with sufficient methanol for 2 h. The red coloured decoction was collected and the process repeated till the colour of extract became light. All collected extracts were pooled and methanol separated by vacuum distillation, yielding 7.21 g of red-brown dye.

Dyeing character: Heartwood chips were dissolved in hot methanol and extracted for 5 h on a water bath with intermittent stirring to obtain the dye bath. After a little cooling, in sufficiently hot dye bath, immersed the textile material and stirred occasionally; simmered for 30 min, temperature raised to around 90°C; cooled the bath; removed the textile material and rinsed thoroughly in distilled water and dried in shade. In case of paper, ordinary paper was used and dye applied by brush. Three pieces of each material were dyed to study effect of ageing, light, and washing. Time intervals of dyeing were so arranged that final study of fresh, 15 days, one month, six months, and one year old samples was carried out the same day. One piece of each was stored in dark, second piece of each was exposed to

sunlight for about 2 h almost every day. Washing of third piece of each was done with a 1% soap solution.

Antimicrobial study: Test organisms were obtained from Department of Botany and Microbiology, Gurukula Kangri University, Haridwar. Bacterial isolates were maintained on nutrient agar slants at 4°C. Antimicrobial study was carried out against six pathogens by filter paper disc diffusion method²². 50 mL nutrient agar was seeded with a 0.5 mL of each of the bacterial culture (O.D. 0.8) and was poured into 90 mm petriplates. Filter paper discs of 5 mm dia, each containing 0.5 mg of dye (through suspension in aqueous methanol) were placed at four different places in inoculated plates. In control plate, discs moistened with aqueous methanol were placed. Petriplates were incubated at 28°C for 24 h.

Indicator studies: Indicator solution was prepared by dissolving 1 g of dye in 100 mL methanol; its pH was determined (Systronics-324) and found to be 4.78. Double distilled water was used. Chemicals were either B.D.H., AnalaR or C.D.H., A.R. quality. Four solutions (0.01, 0.10, 1.00 and 4.00 N) each of HCl, NaOH, CH₃COOH and NH₄OH were used. In each case both the titrations (acid in burette and alkali in burette) were carried out using present natural dye indicator and separately the phenolphthalein or methyl orange (2–3 drops). Strong acid with strong base, strong acid with weak base, weak acid with strong base were titrated. The pH-metric titrations were also performed in each case. Reproducibility was better than $\pm 3\%$. λ_{\max} were determined using Shimadzu UV-Vis 101 spectrophotometer.

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